

A Study on the Ice Bridges & Its Forecasting Methods

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Abstract:

An Ice Bridge is a frozen natural structure formed overseas, bays, rivers or Lake Surfages. They facilitate migration of animals or people over a water body that was previously uncrossible by terrestrial animals, including humans. The most significant Ice Bridges are formed by glaciations, spanning distances of many miles over sometimes relatively deep water bodies. I have conducted many studies on the Bridges and invented the Global Monsoon Time Scale which can help to study and predict the Ice Bridges in advance.

Keywords: Global Monsoon Time Scale, Ice Bridges.

1. INTRODUCTION: By establishing the Global Monsoon Time Scales in accordance with the conditions of a country and maintain, impending Ice Bridge can be studied, estimated and predicted in advance. Here shows an example of method to study and predict such weather conditions.

2. GLOBAL MONSOON TIME SCALE: The global Monsoon Time Scale – a Chronological sequence of events arranged in between time and weather with the help of a scale for studying the past's, present and future movements of monsoon of a country and its relationship with other weather problem and natural calamities.

Prepare the Global Monsoon Time Scale having 365 horizontal days from March 21st to next year March 20th of a required period comprising of a large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The main weather events if any of the country such as Ice Bridge etc. have been entering on the scale as per date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale of a country in this manner continuously, we can study the past, present and future movements of Ice Bridge of a country. I have invented the following global, regional and sub-regional monsoon time scales.

2.1. GLOBAL MONSOON TIME SCALES	2.2. REGIONAL MONSOON TIME SCALES	2.3. SUB-REGIONAL MONSOON TIME SCALES
African Monsoon Time Scale	North American Monsoon Time Scale	South Asian Monsoon Time Scale
North American Monsoon Time Scale	North African Monsoon Time Scale	Maritime Continent Monsoon Time Scale
Asian Monsoon Time Scale	Indian Monsoon Time Scale	East African Monsoon Time Scale
Australian Monsoon Time Scale	Western North Pacific Monsoon Time Scale	West African Monsoon Time Scale
European Monsoon Time Scale	South American Monsoon Time Scale	Indo-Australian Monsoon Time Scale
	South African Monsoon Time Scale	Asian-Australian Monsoon Time Scale
	Australian Monsoon Time Scale	Malaysian Australian Monsoon Time Scale
	East Asian Monsoon Time Scale	Northern Australian Monsoon Time Scale
		Arizona Monsoon Time Scale
		Mexican Monsoon Time Scale
		South-West Monsoon Time Scale
		North-East Monsoon Time Scale
		South East Asian Monsoon Time Scale

3. INDIAN MONSOON TIME SCALE:

3.1.CONSTRUTION: For example, I have prepared the Indian Monsoon Time Scale for study, estimate and predict the Indian monsoon system. Prepare the Scale having 365 horizontal days from 1st April to next year March 31st of 128 years from 1888 to 2016 for the required period comprising of large time and weather have been taken and framed into a square graphic scale. The monsoon pulses in the form of low pressure systems over the Indian region have been entering on the scale in stages by 1 for low, 2 for depression, 3 for storm, 4 for severe storm and 5 for severe storm with core of hurricane winds pertaining to the date and month of the each and every year. If we have been managing the scale in this manner continuously, we can study the past's present's and future's of the India monsoon and its relationship with rainfall and other weather problems & natural calamities in India.

3.2.ANALYSIS: The Indian Monsoon Time Scale reveals many secrets of the monsoon & its relationship with rainfall & other weather problems and natural calamities. For example, some bands, clusters and paths of low pressure systems along with the main paths of the Indian Monsoon (South-west monsoon and north-east monsoon) clearly seen in the map of the Indian monsoon it have been some cut-edge paths passing through its systematic zigzag cycles in ascending and ascending order which causes heavy rains & floods in some years and droughts & famines in another years according to their travel. For example, during 1871-1990's the main path of the Indian Monsoon was rising over June, July, August and creating heavy rains and floods in most years. During 1900-1920's it was falling over August, September and causing low rainfall in many years, During 1920-1965's, it was rising again over July, August, September and resulting good rainfall in more years. During 1965-2004's it was falling over September and causing low rainfall and droughts in many years. At present it is rising upwards over June, July, August, and will be resulting heavy rains & floods in coming years during 2004-2060.

4.HAZARD DETECTION METHOD: The tracking date of main path & other various paths such as south-west monsoon and north-east monsoon etc., of the Indian Monsoon denotes the onset of the monsoon, monsoon pulses or low pressure systems, storms and its consequent secondary hazard Ice Bridge etc.. And also we can find out many more secrets of the Indian monsoon such as droughts, famines, cyclones, heavy rains, floods, real images of the Indian Monsoon, and onset & withdrawals of south west monsoon and north-east monsoon etc. by keen study of the Indian Monsoon Time Scale.

For example, the date of tracking ridge of path is the sign to the impending cyclone and its secondary consequent hazard cyclone etc

Another example, the thin and thick markers on the upper border line of the Indian monsoon time scale are the signs to the impending heavy rains & floods and droughts & floods. The thick marking of clusters of low pressure systems on the Indian monsoon time scale is the sign to the impending heavy rains and floods and the thin marking of clusters of low pressure systems on the Indian monsoon time scale is the sign to the impending droughts and famines.

Furthermore example, the main passage of line of monsoon travel from June to September and September to June are also signs to impending weather conditions of a country. For example, during 1871-1990's the main path of the Indian Monsoon was rising over June, July, August and creating heavy rains and floods in most years. During 1900-1920's it was falling over August, September and causing low rainfall in many years. During 1920-1965s, it was rising again over July, August, September and resulting good rainfall in more years. During 1965-2004's it was falling over September and causing low rainfall and droughts in many years. At present it is rising upwards over June, July, August, and will be resulting heavy rains & floods in coming years during 2004-2060 in India.

These are some examples only. We can find out many more secrets of a country weather conditions by keen study of its monsoon time scale.

5.PRINCIPLE: This is an Astrogeophysical / Astrometeorological phenomenon of effects of astronomical bodies and forces on the earth's geophysical atmosphere. The cause is unknown however the year to year change of movement of axis of the earth inclined at $23\frac{1}{2}$ degrees from vertical to its path around the sun does play a significant role in formation of clusters, bands & paths of the Indian Monsoon and stimulates the Indian weather. The inter-tropical convergence zone at the equator follows the movement of the sun and shifts north of the equator merges with the heat low pressure zone created by the rising heat of the sub-continent due to direct and converging rays of the summer sun on the India Sub-Continent and develops into the monsoon trough and maintain monsoon circulation.

6.CONCLUSION: We can make many more changes in the Global Monsoon Time Scale thus bringing many more methods can be designed to predict the Ice Bridge in advance .

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MAP OF THE INDIAN MONSOON

ANALYSIS OF Years (1888-1983)	ANALYSIS OF Months (JUN/SEP)			
	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER
1888	11222122221	1111	11111111111	1222211111
1889	1122	11	112221221	111221
1890	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1891	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1892	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1893	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1894	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1895	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1896	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1897	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1898	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1899	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1900	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1901	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1902	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1903	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1904	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1905	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1906	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1907	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1908	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1909	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1910	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1911	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1912	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1913	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1914	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1915	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1916	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1917	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1918	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1919	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1920	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1921	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1922	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1923	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1924	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1925	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1926	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1927	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1928	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1929	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1930	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1931	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1932	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1933	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1934	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1935	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1936	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1937	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1938	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
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1940	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1941	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1942	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1943	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1944	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
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1949	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1950	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1951	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1952	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1953	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1954	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
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1961	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1962	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
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1964	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
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1966	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1967	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1968	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1969	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1970	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1971	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1972	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1973	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1974	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1975	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1976	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1977	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1978	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1979	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1980	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1981	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1982	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221
1983	1111121222	1111111111	11	11221

Computerised basic scale from 1888 year to 1983 year for the months of 1st June to September, 31st

path of the systematic cycle of the Indian Monsoon.

Computerised analysed scale from 1888 year to 1983 year for the months of 1st June to September, 31st.